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This paper uses US English (for spelling, punctuation rules and formatting of references).
The Rule of Style is: Turabian (in-text/parenthetical).
The author uses the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8.

RUDIMENTS OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

This first period of study at EUCLID University reiterates the critical importance of good essay writing skills for scholars and researchers. As I go through the introductory study materials, I am reminded of those basic but essential writing skills that several of us learn during an academic program such as this, and unlearn shortly after. Effective written communication is all about saying exactly what you mean in your write-up, without leaving room for misinterpretations or ambiguities. The intended message or content is easily lost and buried within a poorly planned and written academic paper. Interestingly, the same applies to all other forms of written communication.

I am excited about starting this first course (ACA-401D) because; taking the first step is always the most challenging part of any journey. Moreover, in an academic environment, it is one thing to ‘know,’ and quite another to effectively communicate what you know to the instructors and faculty. Effective essay writing skills, just as I have studied in the first period of this course, is one great way to strike this critical balance.

2) THE ACA-401 COURSEPACK

The ACA-401 Coursepack gives a clear direction on how a good academic essay should be written. In the section on “Essay Writing: The Basics,” we are tutored on the dos and don’ts in writing a good academic paper. The study material is broken down into not so clearly delineated sections, beginning with the first, which focuses on the basic rules of essay writing. Other sections of the Coursepack focus on how to write a good paper, how to avoid plagiarism by using referencing, how to cite and reference sources using EUCLID approved style guides, how to distinguish between United Kingdom (UK) and United

States of America (USA) English, how to achieve logical flow in essay writing, common errors that are made in academic papers, and so on.

However, the ACA-401 Coursepack presents some structural challenges. For example, some parts of the Coursepack are presented in prose, others in PowerPoint, with ‘introduction’ and ‘conclusion’ coming in-between sections. These are suggestive that the materials were collated from diverse sources. In addition, for an 83-paged document, it does not have a table of content. The absence of numbering in some pages also makes referencing a bit difficult. Beyond these, the course material is effective in giving a good guidance on how to write an academic paper efficiently and responsibly, especially stressing the need to, and how to avoid plagiarism.

The Coursepack also provides support on some of the style guide changes that have evolved in recent times. For example, I was excited to learn, for the first time, that Chicago style rule now allows, and in fact recommends using the standard American dates format: Month Day, Year; for example, June 26, 1972. Before now, dates in references and notes followed the universal or European format: Day Month Year; for example, 26 June 1972 (EUCLID 2015, 70). No doubt, the ACA-401 Coursepack provides a good refresher that would be invaluable throughout the duration of my Doctorate in Sustainable Development and Diplomacy (DSDD) course.

In addition to this Coursepack, the MS Word templates and essay samples provided by EUCLID have also been very helpful. They provide practical insights into how to apply much of the guidelines presented in the Coursepack. They are additional resources that give guidance on how to structure and manage references in EUCLID-styled academic essays.

3) USEFUL LESSONS LEARNED

As Jodi Picoult, the American author is famously quoted as saying: “you can always edit a bad page. You can’t edit a blank page” (Sceski 2017, par. 1). This quote perfectly sums up some of the useful lessons I have learned from Period 1 of this course. Effective writing is not about being a ‘professional’ writer from the outset. It is about effective planning, research, organising your thoughts and ideas, ensuring structural and logical cohesion, ensuring consistency with the adopted use of English and referencing style, as well as thoroughly and painstakingly editing the final output. Writing an essay is one thing; ensuring a well-written essay comes with the additional task of checking, double-checking and paying close attention to every detail. The quality of academic papers is significantly improved by such painstaking proofreading (EUCLID 2015, 5).

The need to avoid plagiarism by ensuring effective referencing is also clearly detailed in the ACA-401 Coursepack: “all academic essays MUST contain references. Referencing guards against plagiarism, a serious academic offence” (EUCLID 2015, 5). At this level of academic pursuit, it is critical to adopt best practices in essay writing and avoid using the intellectual property of other writers without giving them credit for it. The gravity of this

offence and the possible consequences is also flagged in the Coursepack (EUCLID 2015, 12).

4) SO, WHAT IS NEXT?

The Arrangement of courses in the program roadmap at EUCLID, which starts with ACA-401 is indeed brilliant. For someone that had not been involved in any major academic work since 2014, my studies during Period 1 of ACA-401 is reviving the research and academic writing gene that had been dormant in me for over five (5) years. I will now begin to practice the writing guidelines, especially the Turabian rule of style guide, which, I must confess, I will be using for the very first time. Fortunately, I have used the American Psychological Association (APA) referencing style in previous academic programs. I also see a lot of similarities between the two styles.

Another area of weakness that I would need to improve on is mastering the differences between United Kingdom and United States' use of English. Pages 54 to 59 of the Coursepack offers eye-opening guide on several differences that exist between the two, much of which we usually take for granted in essay writing.

Furthermore, the EUCLID Zotero training is god-sent. I intend to master and use this tool copiously throughout this program. It enables me to auto-generate reference notes and bibliography; spell-check my essay using the adopted style of English; and, very importantly, auto-generate my table of content, which is usually a time-consuming task. Zotero is indeed an awesome tool for today's scholars and researchers. As I watched the EUCLID video on Zotero, I could not believe that I was learning about this tool for the first time. It is one tool that I intend to leverage for improved citations and for its many other features.

5) CONCLUSION

I have found the EUCLID ACA-401 Coursepack a useful guide and refresher in writing academic essays. It focuses on much of the important areas in essay writing, with special emphasis on aspects that scholars and researchers usually struggle with. I have learned some very useful lessons from this Coursepack that would come in handy as I go through my other DSDD courses.

However, the Coursepack comes with some challenges, which are mostly structural. For example, there are no numbering in some pages, no table of content, among other shortcomings that could make referencing somewhat challenging. But overall, the course material served the purpose.

I feel better prepared to take on the other courses that are ahead of me in this academic journey, even as I strive to improve on areas of weaknesses that Period 1 studies have thrown up.

REFERENCES

EUCLID University. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Retrieved from: <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed July 3, 2019).

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